

Combined Linguistic and Sensor Models For Machine Learning

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Abstract—this work builds on a cognitive theory called dynamic logic and considers the relationship between language and cognition. We explore the idea of dual models that combine linguistic and sensor features. We demonstrate that simultaneous learning of textual and image data results in formation of meaningful concepts and subsequent improvement in concept recognition.

Keywords—*Unsupervised Learning, Language and Cognition, Dynamic Logic, LUPI*

I. INTRODUCTION

This work builds on a cognitive theory proposed in [1], called dynamic logic, also referred to as neural modeling fields (NMF), and modeling fields theory (MFT) in other publications [2] [3] [4] [5] [6]. This is a cognitively inspired mathematical framework providing a generic way of finding an optimal match between a set of parametric probabilistic models and sensor input data. The probabilistic models provide the ability to include a priori knowledge and to model the variability of real world data. The match is obtained by maximizing the similarity between the models and the data. A key feature of dynamic logic is the vague-to-crisp process [7], which begins by assigning almost equal association weights between the models and the data. Such process results in efficient computation and helps avoid local maxima. Empirical evidence confirming the existence of such processes in the brain was found during neuro-imaging experiments [8].

The foundational idea of dynamic logic is that the vague-to-crisp processes take place when we recognize objects through our senses. By mimicking this recognition process, a mathematical dynamic logic framework has been used in numerous publications related to signal and image processing where its ability to separate useful signals from noise proved crucial. Most of the engineering applications of dynamic logic involve processing sensor data with deterministic parts of the models specified as mathematical relations. For example, a typical application in target tracking utilizes certain motion models, such as motion with constant acceleration.

Dynamic logic also proposes that longer term vague-to-crisp learning processes take place in the human brain as we learn new concepts. Language must play an important role in such learning. Every concept that we perceive in the world around us has a corresponding linguistic description. This

description may consist of a single word or may consist of a complicated explanation. The process by which we are able to learn the associations between words and concepts is currently unknown. It appears that the conventional statistical learning is not adequate due to enormous number of possible mappings between the objects and the words [9]. Cognitive scientists agree that some inborn ability to learn the language and the perceptual models together must exist [9] [10].

Dynamic logic makes the connection between language and cognition by conjecturing the existence of dual models [10]. This means that every concept that a human learns has two parts – linguistic and cognitive. The two parts are connected from birth. Both models are updated using the vague-to-crisp mechanism. The fact that the two parts of the concept are linked from the beginning solves the association problem by getting rid of it. Note that dynamic logic describes only the potential connections between the linguistic and cognitive models as inborn. The models themselves: the words and the objects – are learned from experience.

It is well known that our linguistic abilities develop faster than the corresponding cognitive understanding. As it is noticed in [10], Ch. 4, a 5 year old child is able to use words that describe concepts that he or she is not capable of comprehending until much later in life. In the context of dual models, this observation leads to an interesting conclusion. It seems that the linguistic part of the dual model is learned first and is subsequently used to guide the learning of the cognitive part. Practically, this stems from the fact that the linguistic data are readily available as we are immersed in the ocean of text and speech. This availability of linguistic data allows to quickly learn the linguistic parts of the models.

In this work, we investigate the idea of dual models by implementing a dynamic logic algorithm for dual models. As an example, we consider the task of learning to recognize handwritten digits, which is essentially the task of learning a classifier with 10 classes. Supervised handwritten digits classification is a well-known problem in machine learning and highly accurate classifiers have been built [11]. In this work we are interested in demonstrating how the concepts of the 10 digits could arise in an unsupervised fashion. The main thesis is that the acquisition of correct concepts is guided by including textual descriptions of the digits as part of the training data.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the mathematical mechanism of dynamic logic. Section III focuses on the model selection aspect of dynamic logic. Section IV describes the dual models. Section V presents the results of the handwritten digits experiments. Section VI is the discussion of the results and the paper is concluded in Section VII.

II. DYNAMIC LOGIC

Mathematically, dynamic logic considers a general problem of finding the best match between a set of models $\mathbf{M} = \{M_1, \dots, M_H\}$ that depend on a set of parameters $\theta = \{S_1, \dots, S_H\}$ and a set of data inputs $\mathbf{X} = \{X_1, \dots, X_N\}$ [1]. One of the challenges of this task is the inherent exponential computational complexity of data-to-model association. This difficulty is overcome using a vague-to-crisp process of simultaneous data association and parameter estimation. This process is expressed mathematically as the maximization of the following total similarity.

$$L(\mathbf{X}|\theta) = \prod_{n=1}^N \sum_{h=1}^H r_h l(x_n, M_h) \quad (1)$$

Here the similarity between a data element x_n and a model M_h is measured by a function $l(x_n, M_h)$, and the total similarity is given as a product over all the data and a summation over all the models. The quantities r_h are the relative weights of the models. The mathematical form of the models reflects the prior knowledge and the model parameter values are estimated based on the evidence given by the data. The models are often defined in probabilistic terms as probability density functions depending on parameters S_h . In this case the similarity between the data element x_n and the model M_h is given by the likelihood of observing the data given the model.

$$l(x_n, M_h) \equiv p(x_n | S_h) \quad (2)$$

The maximization of (1) is achieved by iterative evaluation (3) of the model parameters and the special quantities f_{hn} referred to as association weights. In (3) α is a gradient ascent constant. The association weights f_{hn} are computed based on the current values of parameters S_h and the parameters are recomputed in the estimation step based on the current association weights.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Association} \quad f_{hn} &= \frac{r_h l(n, h)}{\sum_{h_2=1}^H r_{h_2} l(n, h_2)} \\ \text{Estimation} \quad S_h^{t+1} &= S_h^t + \alpha \sum_{n=1}^N f_{hn} \frac{\partial \log l(n, h)}{\partial S_h} \\ r_h &= \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N f_{hn}}{N} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Each iteration step increases the value of the objective function and it can be shown that it converges to a (possibly local) maximum of $L(\mathbf{X}, \theta)$. There are two important additions to the iterative procedure (3) that make it unique and efficient.

1) *Initialization*. The model parameters must be initialized in such a way that the initial association weights are almost the same for all models and all data elements. This is the vague initialization postulated by *dynamic logic*.

2) *Vagueness control*. A special mechanism may be

introduced into the models to allow for controlled decrease in vagueness of data association.

Our recent work [2] introduced a third mechanism to the dynamic logic framework, related to model selection.

3) *Competition among models*. A special mechanism is introduced for inducing competition among models resulting in correct model selection.

The next section describes the model selection mechanism in detail.

III. MODEL SELECTION AND ACCELERATED MAP

Dynamic logic, just like most of the unsupervised learning techniques, faces the problem of model selection. If the data are modeled by a mixture of statistical models, how many models should the mixture include? Is it possible to automatically find an optimal number of models? In [2], the mechanism of model selection was introduced in dynamic logic framework. The proposed algorithm, referred to as accelerated MAP, or AMAP, is so far limited to a specific case of the dynamic logic algorithm where the models are multivariate Bernoulli distributions.

Denote the number of individual observations (data points) in the data set by N . Individual observation is denoted by x_n , $n=1 \dots N$. Each observation is a D -dimensional binary vector, with elements $x_{nd} \in \{0,1\}$, $d=1 \dots D$. Each element of the binary vector is modeled by the Bernoulli distribution, which is a discrete probability distribution taking the value 1 with probability p_{hd} , where h is the model index. The elements of the binary vector are assumed to be statistically independent. Under such assumption, the probability of observing vector x_n conditional on model S_h is given as follows.

$$p(x_n | S_h) = \prod_{d=1}^D p_{hd}^{x_{nd}} (1 - p_{hd})^{1-x_{nd}} \quad (4)$$

In AMAP, the objective function (1) is modified by adding the penalty term, as follows.

$$L_r(\mathbf{X}|\theta) = L(\mathbf{X}|\theta) + Q(\theta). \quad (5)$$

The penalty term $Q(\theta)$ is formulated to encourage setting the magnitudes of the Bernoulli parameters to zero. Setting all of the parameters p_{hd} to zero for some h results in "turning off" the corresponding model M_h , and thus reducing the complexity of the solution.

The logarithm of the modified objective function is given as follows.

$$L_r(\mathbf{X}|\theta) = \sum_{n=1}^N \log \sum_{h=1}^H r_h p(x_n | h) + \sum_{h=1}^H \sum_{d=1}^D \log g(p_{hd}) \quad (6)$$

Function $g(p_{hd})$ is chosen to have small values for p_{hd} close to 0 and large values for p_{hd} close to 1. In particular, the following form of the penalty function, corresponding to the beta distribution, was used:

$$g_b(p_{hd}) = \frac{(1 - p_{hd})^{b-1}}{B(1, b)}. \quad (7)$$

Here, b is the distribution parameters and B is the beta function. The parameter b dictates the amount of tradeoff between the quality of the data-to-model match and the complexity of the models. If the value of b is too large, all the models will be turned off. If the value is too small, the penalty will not be enough to turn off all the unnecessary models. Finding the proper value for b is difficult since it likely depends on the data.

The key idea behind AMAP is the use of a variable parameter b . The parameter starts with small values and gradually increases. Such strategy is referred to as acceleration. Although the unlimited increase of the parameter b results in turning off all of the models, it was shown that if the penalty parameter b is increased slowly enough, the algorithm's behavior indicates when b is in the neighborhood of its optimal value. It was observed in numeric simulations that the algorithm goes through a series of "stable phases", during which the number of models turned off does not change. Such stable phases serve as basis for model selection. Detailed description of AMAP can be found in [2], where the stable stages are studied analytically and numerically.

AMAP has been used for text categorization, which explains the utilization of Bernoulli model. It is a standard practice for a corpus of text documents to be modelled as a binary word usage matrix. Each document is represented as a binary input vector x_n of length D , where D is the number of distinct words encountered in the corpus. Previous work [2] applied AMAP to the 20 newsgroups collection [12]. The results show that AMAP was at least as successful or sometimes more successful in finding the document clusters in these data as the other state of the art methods used for comparison.

IV. DUAL MODELS

The integration of language and cognition in dynamic logic framework is achieved through the use of dual models. As described in [10], every model M_h now consists of two parts, cognitive and linguistic:

$$M_h = \{M_h^C, M_h^L\} \quad (8)$$

The linguistic part of our models is constructed just like the model used for text categorization. Indeed, we assume that each linguistic input is represented by a binary input vector x_n^L and the length of this vector corresponds to the number of distinct words in some dictionary, D^L . In general, D^L is a large number; however it may be reduced depending on particular applications.

The cognitive model M_h^C has to be specific to the sensing modality. We focus on the visual perceptions, therefore our sensor data are essentially images, and the corresponding input vectors x_n^C contain the values of the features extracted from input images by varieties of techniques studied by computer vision. The size of these vectors, D^L , may also be extremely large, although this depends on particulars of the computer vision techniques employed.

V. EXAMPLE OF DIGITS LEARNING

Consider the problem of learning to recognize the handwritten digits. As the source of image data, we use MNIST [11], which is a standard dataset with large numbers of training and testing samples. Our goal is to demonstrate how the presence of linguistic components in the models improves learning. With this goal in mind, we chose to extract only simple image features. This allows keeping the quality of baseline learning low enough to observe significant improvements by introducing the dual models.

Handwritten digits classification is a well-known problem in pattern recognition. The use of MNIST greatly simplifies the problem due to the fact that each digit is given as a separate image of standard size, and there is no noise and no background-foreground separation problem. Nevertheless, the variability within each class of our 10-class recognition problem is large due to different styles of handwriting.

For the purposes of this investigation, we will treat each digit as a complex concept that can be given a textual description. The description may refer to different aspects of the digits, such as their shape, their relationship with other concepts, etc. One way to obtain such a description is by asking a person to describe the shape of a digit and any other associations that the digit brings to mind. This would be an extremely time-consuming process.

We opted to make the textual descriptions using one of the available corpuses of text data. The Corpus of Contemporary American English (COCA) is the largest freely-available corpus of English [13]. It allows searching for specific words and for surrounding words, called collocates.

Fig. 1 Example of a text description attached to digit "two".

For example, entering the word "two" into the COCA search interface returns a list of top 100 words (collocates) that are encountered within up to 10 words before or after the word "two". For each collocate COCA provides text sources, including the complete phrases that contain the collocates. Randomly sampling the phrases we can compose a text containing words that frequently occur in the vicinity of the word "two". An example of the kind of textual description that

is obtained can be seen in Fig.1. This textual description can be transformed into a binary usage vector.

We used the following procedure for making textual descriptions and corresponding binary vectors with COCA.

A. For each digit

- 1) Find the top 8 collocates
- 2) For each collocate, make a list of its top 100 collocates.
- 3) Extract sentences containing the collocates from the previous step

B. Compile the full list of collocates for all 10 digits.

Our complete list of collocates contained 434 words. In order to generate the input vectors, we randomly sample from the list of the corresponding collocates. Table I shows the list of top 8 words for each of the digits.

The digits are given by 28 x 28 grayscale bitmaps. We threshold each bitmaps at pixel value 100 to obtain a binary image. We then transform the image into a one-dimensional vector. Each component of the vector is a Boolean variable indicating whether the corresponding pixel belongs to the digit. Using binary images allows utilizing the same Bernoulli model for the cognitive part of the digit model.

In summary, we have the Bernoulli linguistic model with $D^L = 434$, and the Bernoulli image model with $D^C = 784$.

We combine both models into the digit model with $784+434=1218$ dimensions. This is the dual model discussed in the previous section. Next we experiment with this combined model by varying some of the parameters.

Below is the list of factors that affect the results of learning.

- A. Text data included/not included
- B. The initial number of models, K
- C. Acceleration on/off
- D. Accelerated MAP parameters
- E. Size of the training data set

The size of the training set was fixed to 2000, with roughly 200 images for each digit. The accelerated MAP parameters were also fixed using the methodology described in [2]. Thus we only studied the effect of the first three factors.

The idea of AMAP is to set the initial number of models to be larger than the expected “true” number of classes or clusters in the data. As the algorithm executes, the unnecessary models turn off and the result contains the optimal solution. However, even if AMAP is not used, some models may still turn off especially when large numbers of models are used.

In the first experiment, we do not include the textual descriptions and turn the acceleration on. This means that the dataset has only 784 dimensions. We start with $K=25$ models. The result of learning is shown in Fig. 2. The figure shows all 25 models, and we can see that only 4 of them remained active. The blue squares correspond to the models that were turned off by setting all of their parameters to zero. The algorithm was

not able to separate between the 10 digits and thus did not learn the right concepts.

Fig. 2 Results of learning the 10 digits, no textual descriptions are given, and accelerated MAP was used. The algorithm did not learn the right concepts.

The second experiment started with $K=25$ models but included the textual descriptions of the digits. Accelerated MAP was on. The result, shown in Fig. 3 shows that in this case, the algorithm converged to the correct number of models and thus successfully learned the 10 digits, even though they were not explicitly labelled.

In the next two experiments the initial number of models was set to $K=100$ and the AMAP was not used. Fig. 4 shows the results without text and Fig. 5 shows the results with text. In these two cases the final number of models is much larger than 10 and it is hard to decide which learning was more successful. In order to evaluate the models, we use them to build classifiers and compute their classification accuracy. The simplest approach is to use them as naïve Bayesian classifiers. Recall that after learning, we can assign each training sample to one of the models, used the association weights f_{hn} . Since we know the true labels for the training set, each of the learned models can be assigned a label based on the labels of the majority of its samples.

Fig. 3 Results of learning the 10 digits, with textual descriptions, and accelerated MAP was used. The algorithm successfully learned the right concepts.

Naïve Bayesian classifier computes the conditional probability $p(x_n|S_h)$ for the test sample x_n , for each model S_h and assigns the sample to the model that has the maximum conditional probability. A testing dataset was generated using digits different from the ones used for training. The size of the

testing dataset was 500, or an average of 50 digits for each class. Note that the testing set consists only from the image data, there is no linguistic component.

Fig. 4 Results of learning the 10 digits, no textual descriptions, and accelerated MAP was not used.

Fig. 5 Results of learning the 10 digits, with textual descriptions, and accelerated MAP was not used.

The results of classification for all experiments are given in Table II. This table also includes the case of $K=25$ and no acceleration, which resulted in all models remaining active at the end. These results show interesting trends that agree with expectations. Indeed, the comparison between the first and the third row of Table II shows that the presence of textual description resulted in learning a significantly better classifier. The accuracy of the dual model classifier is 90% versus the accuracy of the image-only model at 75%.

VI. DISCUSSION

The underlying assumptions of this work are that a) the brain uses a learning mechanism postulated by dynamic logic, and b) potential connections between linguistic and perceptual concept models are inborn. The actual connections are estimated from the data. Numerical experiments with handwritten digits were designed to emphasize these assumptions.

We assume a simplified mechanism for sensory perception where the features of the images are just the individual pixels and no advanced feature extraction is performed. This is done in order to keep low baseline quality of learning. Under these

assumptions, the results of handwritten digit learning experiments show that the inclusion of linguistic descriptions with the digits is advantageous and can be interpreted in accordance with the predictions made by earlier publications.

TABLE I. TOP TERMS IN DIGIT DESCRIPTIONS

	Terms
0	round, oval, perfect, smooth, continuous, curved, symmetrical, closed
1	vertical, upward, longitudinal, perpendicular, linear, slender, directional, thin
2	round, top, sharp, bottom, flat, foot, swan, pointy
3	top, bottom, similar, wavy, smooth, sharp, middle, open
4	open, top, one, foot, right, sharp, upside, down
5	hook, top, round, asymmetrical, flat, roof, curvilinear, open
6	circle, bottom, curved, top, closed, tangent, smooth, round
7	flat, roof, vertical, foot, sharp, right, straight, tilted
8	two, circle, oval, womanly, bottom, voluptuous, symmetrical, infinity
9	top, circle, oval, bottom, curve, tangent, closed, smooth

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION ACCURACY*

With Text?	With AMAP?	K	H	Accuracy
No	No	100	93	75%
Yes	No	25	25	85%
Yes	No	100	90	90%
Yes	Yes	25	10	79%
No	Yes	25	4	NA

*K is the initial number of models, and H is the number of learned concepts

In particular, we make the following observations:

1. Learning the correct digits concepts without textual descriptions was unsuccessful. In the case when AMAP regularization was not used and a large number of models were learned, the classification accuracy of the learned models was only at 75%. With AMAP turned on, the process converged to 4 final models, obviously not corresponding to the 10 digits. This means that the configuration with 10 digits is not stable enough to be learned by the AMAP algorithm.

2. Learning the digits with textual descriptions resulted in significantly higher classification accuracy, which is interpreted as learning correct concepts. The best accuracy in our experiments was achieved when a large number of models

were learned without regularization. When AMAP was used, the classification accuracy was higher comparing to learning without text.

3. Learning with text and AMAP regularization resulted in learning the right number of models: 10 models for 10 digits. Even though the classification accuracy of the resulting models was lower, this result is significant because it demonstrates that both the language and the model selection mechanisms may be essential for learning correct associations between the objects in the real world and their cognitive models.

This contribution is the first attempt to implement the dual models as proposed by dynamic logic. The results should be extended in the following ways.

Firstly, the methodology for obtaining textual descriptions for images could be improved by better utilizing COCA and perhaps other corpora. Another direction is to collect descriptions from people by using speech recognition software.

The models used in this work are fairly simple and could be improved. On the linguistic side, we are considering hierarchical models obtained by Latent Dirichlet Allocation techniques [14]. Another interesting direction would be to develop linguistic models based on the notion of semantic family resemblance, as advocated in [15]. On the image processing side, more advanced features and object models should be utilized as well, especially if the dataset is expanded beyond handwritten digits.

Current models learn in batch mode, processing all of the available data at the same time. This is obviously not how humans learn in real world. Linguistic and sensory inputs usually are processed one at a time. The transformation of the current dynamic logic framework into an online learning framework has been the subject of recent work [16]. That work may be developed further by incorporating the concept of dual models.

Finally, we would like to connect this contribution with another idea from the machine learning community. A new paradigm, called Learning Using Privileged Information (LUPI) has been proposed in [17]. The idea of LUPI is to imitate the process of learning with a teacher who provides additional (privileged) information during the training that is not available during testing. The implementation of LUPI is an extension of Support Vector Machines (SVM's) [18], called SVM+. In this implementation, the privileged information is utilized to better position the classification hyper-plane. The linguistic data could be considered as privileged information and thus the dual models can be interpreted as an alternative implementation of the LUPI paradigm.

VII. CONCLUSION

The question of how the language and sensory perceptions are related is of great interest to both cognitive scientists and the machine learning community. Cognitive scientists look for explanations of our abilities to learn the meaning of words by associating them with objects in the real world. Machine learning researchers are interested in better ways of exploiting large amounts of data often composed of both sensor outputs and textual descriptions. In this contribution, the dynamic logic

approach to combining linguistic and cognitive learning has been considered. The results of learning demonstrate how the inclusion of linguistic information into the training process results in creation of meaningful concept models.

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